

SolDAC

FULL SPECTRUM SOLAR DIRECT
AIR CAPTURE & CONVERSION

<https://soldac-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101069359.

Innovate
UK

This project has received funding from UK Research and Innovation - Innovate UK under Innovation Funding Service (ISF) 10059331 and 10038044.

SoIDAC's main ambition is to reinvent the ethylene industry, which is the chemical industry's primary building block, by proving an emerging breakthrough technology for producing technically and economically competitive and climate-neutral sustainable ethylene and by-product ethanol from solar energy and air.

The **Photo-Electrochemical Conversion unit (PEC)** allows the **direct conversion of carbon dioxide into ethylene**. This unit exploits bandwidth-selected light from a **solar collector (FSS)** that splits the solar spectrum **for electricity and heat generation** at efficiency higher than standalone PV modules and standalone

solar thermal collectors. Heat is used in an innovative **direct air capture (DAC)** unit at ultralow temperature (~60 °C), fostering the eventual circular integration with heat networks. The **DAC unit removes carbon dioxide from the air**, concentrates it to more than 95% and compresses it to feed the PEC stack and a pipeline for carbon dioxide storage.

This allows the carbon footprint of the whole sun-to-chemicals process to be offset and enables gain in carbon credits, **opening an opportunity to exceed climate-neutrality and produce carbon-negative by-product ethanol**. The process offered by SoIDAC is energetically self-sufficient, economically viable and carbon-negative on the condition that each unit (DAC, PEC, FSS) reaches new targets in efficiency.

BEFORE SoIDAC

AFTER SoIDAC

Objectives

The overall objective of the SoLDAC project is to prove the production of carbon-neutral ethylene and by-product ethanol (C2 products) from the air in an independent off-grid decentralized and market-competitive process powered by solar energy.

01

Produce carbon-neutral ethylene and by-product ethanol from the air in an independent off-grid decentralized and market-competitive process powered by solar energy.

02

Guarantee the techno-economic feasibility of the SoLDAC process through the three enhanced units that comprise the process.

03

Demonstrate through eco-design the reduction of the "cradle to grave" carbon-footprint of the SoLDAC individual process units.

04

Popularise Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCUS) technologies in society.

05

Inform key stakeholders within the energy and chemicals sectors and general public of project findings through targeted events and the efficient use of different media.

06

Enhance Europe-based global leadership in the production of renewable chemicals from CO₂.

Impacts

Removing CO₂ from air and using it as raw material to generate commodity chemicals, powering the whole process with 100% renewable solar energy in an unassisted and decentralized fashion.

Improvements in the Direct Air Capture unit (DAC)

- New family of step-isotherm materials for CO₂ sorption
- Materials become benchmark in DAC and other carbon capture applications
- CHEX (coated heat-exchangers) technology becomes the standard in DAC
- Unlock utilisation of waste heat and solar heat in cold climates
- Expectation that DAC will absorb < 20% of the renewable energy generated in 2050

Improvements in the Photo-Electrochemical Conversion unit (PEC)

- Ethylene levelised cost lower than fossil fuel process (< 1€/kg)
- Unlock electrolysis as an option for ethylene production

Improvements in the Full-Spectrum Solar collector (FSS)

- New paradigm in solar energy generation by decoupling light collection and electricity generation

Integrated SoLDAC process

- Decarbonization of the ethylene industry. SoLDAC market penetration enabling ethylene industry to become zero-carbon

Lab testing

Development of the validation lab infrastructure, component integration and full testing of SoLDAC: infrastructure for solar light harvesting, cold light provision, and thermal energy production and storage.

Consortium

SoLDAC consortium is composed of 8 partners from 4 different countries chosen to form a well-balanced and complementary set of research organizations (RTO's/UNI) and to exploit the expertise of some SMEs in the renewable technology field.

COMET GLOBAL INNOVATION

Project Coordinator. COMET will lead the commissioning and testing of SoLDAC integrated process (WP5). In addition, COMET will lead communication and dissemination activities as Communication Manager.

CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE

WP3, development of materials and components for the water harvester in the SoLDAC unit, modelling of SoLDAC system.

EIM. EUROPEAN INNOVATION MARKETPLACE

Lead and coordination of Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Capacity Building activities (WP7), including the definition of Exploitation and Business strategy roadmaps (T7.3) and Clustering activities and EU policies immersion (T7.5).

IREC

IREC leads the development of the photoelectrochemical device for CO₂ valorization to C₂ products in WP4. or this, IREC will develop materials and (photo)electrodes and will design and fabricate the electrochemical stack. Additionally, IREC will participate in further integration with DAC and FSS technologies in WP5.

Consortium

LOMARTOV

LOMARTOV will lead the triple sustainability validation (environmental, economic and social) of the SoLDAC solution (WP6), applying Eco-design principles and Life Cycle Assessment from raw materials selection, through operation and end-of-life stages. Moreover, LOM will lead capacity building and best practices exchange tasks and support the dissemination and exploitation activities.

UNIVERSITAT DE LLEIDA

The University of Lleida (UdL) leads the development of the Full Spectrum Solar (FSS) unit for concentrating the incident sunlight, managing the concentrated photons by spectral splitting and converting the concentrated photon flux either to electricity or heat simultaneously (WP2). The filtered concentrated photons will be transmitted to any photo-active downstream process with the specific range of wavelengths selected by a fiber bundle. In addition, the benchmarking validation lab, where the whole technology will be tested, will be located at the UdL facilities.

UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH

The University of Edinburgh designs, builds and tests one low-grade-heat powered device for capturing, purify and compress carbon dioxide directly from the atmosphere (direct air capture). Its tasks include engineering efficient components that integrate nanoporous materials exposed to small temperature swing between ambient temperature and 60°C. The University of Edinburgh develops also catalysts for conversion of atmospheric carbon dioxide to Ethylene.

UNIVERSITY ST ANDREWS

Preparation and characterisation of nanoporous zeolites and metal organic framework materials, known and novel, to act as selective and reversible solid sorbents for carbon dioxide.

Coordinator :

Partners :

Associated partners :

THE UNIVERSITY
of EDINBURGH

University of
St Andrews

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